

Phenanthroline-functionalized graphene as a ligand platform for single-atom catalysis

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ABSTRACT

The precise anchoring of single metal atoms on solid supports remains a key challenge in the design of single-atom catalysts (SACs), particularly for carbon-based materials where metal coordination environments are often poorly defined. We report a graphene-based support covalently functionalized with 1,10-phenanthroline-5-amine groups via nucleophilic substitution on fluorographene in DMSO. This approach introduces well-defined chelating sites that enable the rational and selective immobilization of transition metals. A copper-based SAC was synthesized by impregnating the functionalized graphene with a CuCl₂ solution. Spectroscopic and microscopic analyses confirmed the formation of atomically dispersed Cu(I) species coordinated by phenanthroline ligands, with no detectable nanoparticle formation. The resulting catalyst exhibited high activity in the Chan–Lam coupling of 1H-imidazole with phenylboronic acid, achieving a turnover frequency of 3.8 h⁻¹, and outperformed heterogeneous benchmark systems, including commercial CuO nanoparticles. However, recyclability tests revealed a decline in catalytic activity after four cycles, primarily due to the leaching of Cu-phenanthroline complexes. These findings demonstrate the potential of functionalized graphene as a platform for developing SACs with well-defined coordination environments. Nevertheless, enhancing catalyst stability, e.g., through secondary anchoring strategies, optimized metalation protocols, or post-synthetic stabilization, is needed for future industrial applications.

1. Introduction

Single-atom catalysis (SAC) has rapidly emerged as a transformative field in heterogeneous catalysis, uniquely combining maximal atomic efficiency, distinct electronic properties, and catalyst processability and recovery [1]. Despite significant advances, one of the fundamental challenges in the field remains the precise and reproducible control over the anchoring sites of single metal atoms onto solid supports. Current preparation strategies for SACs, which include impregnation [2,3], defect engineering [3], or pyrolysis [4,5], generally result in a heterogeneous distribution of active sites, due to uncontrolled metal deposition and poorly defined coordination environments. These methods inherently rely on a trial-and-error approach and require an extensive empirical optimization for deployable SAC.

Recent theoretical and experimental studies have highlighted a critical trade-off between catalytic activity and stability of single atoms, underlining the necessity for more precise and rational control of their coordination environment [6]. Specifically, the coordination sphere and oxidation state of single atoms strongly dictate their catalytic efficiency and selectivity. For example, single Pt atoms demonstrate optimal catalytic activity in ammonia borane dehydrogenation when possessing a high oxidation state or a larger population of unoccupied 5d orbitals [7]. These findings underline the importance of strategies that enable well-defined and controllable single-atom sites. This need is further supported by the emerging concept of smart single-atom catalysts, which seek to exploit the inherent dynamic behavior of isolated atoms in response to external stimuli, allowing for adaptable and optimized catalytic function under working conditions [8].

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Ligand-assisted immobilization of single atoms offers a promising route towards achieving site-specific anchoring with well-defined coordination geometries. Such strategies draw inspiration from coordination chemistry, particularly the design principles of heteroleptic inorganic complexes, to tailor the electronic and geometric properties of single atoms anchored onto surfaces [9]. Although ligand-based approaches have been explored primarily in metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) [10], their extension to carbon-based supports, particularly graphene derivatives, remains underdeveloped, despite the substantial potential offered by these materials. Graphene derivatives present attractive properties, including exceptional surface area, tunable chemical reactivity, and electronic conductivity, rendering them ideal for catalytic support applications [11].

In this context, fluorographene emerges as a uniquely versatile precursor material for graphene derivatives due to its exceptional chemical reactivity towards nucleophilic substitution reactions accompanied by simultaneous defluorination [12]. Functionalization of fluorographene thus enables covalent incorporation of ligand-like moieties onto graphene sheets, which can act as highly selective binding sites for single metal atoms. This approach potentially resolves the critical challenge of site heterogeneity, stabilizing single atoms against aggregation by precise covalent attachment [13–15].

Herein, we introduce a robust ligand-assisted approach to synthesize single-atom catalysts using ligand-functionalized graphene derived from fluorographene. Specifically, we covalently anchored 1,10-phenanthroline-5-amine onto the graphene surface, providing bidentate chelating sites suitable for precise coordination of transition metal ions. Moreover, our synthetic protocol significantly advances the sustainability and safety profile of graphene functionalization, replacing traditional toxic solvents such as *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) or *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) with dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and triethylamine. This method achieves high degrees of functionalization and complete defluorination, yielding stable, fluorine-free graphene-based materials.

The effectiveness of the synthesized ligand-functionalized graphene was demonstrated via immobilization of Cu(II) ions from aqueous CuCl₂, forming stable and well-defined single-atom sites. The catalytic competence and stability of the resulting material were validated in the Chan–Lam coupling reaction between imidazole and phenylboronic acid. Our findings confirm not only the efficacy of ligand-assisted immobilization for precise metal anchoring but also the substantial catalytic performance improvements achievable through well-defined coordination environments. The described strategy also opens new pathways toward a new class of SACs.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Graphite (fluorinated, polymer, GrF), copper(II) chloride dihydrate (CuCl₂·2H₂O, >99 %), nitrobenzene (>99 %), triethylamine (Et₃N, >99 %), copper(II) oxide (nanoparticles, <50 nm), 1,10-phenanthroline (>99 %), copper(I) iodide (CuI, 98 %), phenylboronic acid (>97 %), imidazole (>99.8 %), 1-phenylimidazole (>97 %), dimethyl sulfone (TraceCERT®) were purchased from Merck (Sigma Aldrich), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO, >99 %), acetone (>99 %), and methanol (MeOH, >99 %) from VWR chemicals, hydrochloric acid (HCl, aqueous, 35 wt%) and copper(I) chloride (CuCl, pure) from Penta, potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃, >99 %) from Alfa Aesar, and 1,10-phenanthroline-5-amine (PhenA, >98 %) from TCI. Cyanographene (G-CN) has been synthesized according to the previously described procedure [16].

2.2. Synthesis of graphene functionalized with phenanthroline

In a 500 mL round-bottom flask containing 250 mL of DMSO, 5 g of GrF (161.5 mmol of CF) was dispersed, sonicated for 4 h, and then stirred overnight. Then, 2.45 g of PhenA (12.55 mmol, ca 1/13 of the CF

amount) was added to the prepared FG dispersion in DMSO while stirring, followed by the addition of 13.4 g of K₂CO₃ (97 mmol). Finally, 40 mL of Et₃N (287 mmol) was added to the mixture while stirring. The solid materials were washed down from the neck of the flask with an additional 10 mL of DMSO. The mixture was refluxed at 130 °C for 3 days. Then, the material was acquired through centrifugation and washed with DMSO, acetone, EtOH, water (ultrapure, UP), acidic water (containing HCl, pH~2.5), and water until the conductivity of the supernatants was below 100 μS·cm⁻¹. The material was then redispersed in UP water and dialysed for 3 weeks. Finally, the purified material was freeze-dried, obtaining a black powder. The material was denoted as G-Phen.

2.3. Copper anchoring

The copper anchoring was done according to the procedure described previously [13]. Briefly, 240 mg of the material was dispersed in 20 mL of UP water and sonicated for 30 min. After this, 2 mL of aqueous solution containing 120 mg of copper was added to the dispersion while stirring. The mixture was stirred for 24 h. After this, the material was purified via centrifugation and washing with water until the conductivity of the discarded supernatant was below 50 μS·cm⁻¹. The material was redispersed in water and further purified using dialysis for 1 day. Then, the aqueous dispersion was freeze-dried, obtaining black powder. The material was denoted as G-Phen-Cu. The procedure was optionally scaled up. Three batches of G-Phen-Cu were prepared. The ICP-MS contents of copper within the different batches of the catalyst were determined to be 3.87, 4.32, and 4.78 wt%. Copper anchoring on G-CN, done in the same way, resulted in 3.53 wt% of copper within the resulting G-CN-Cu.

2.4. Instrumental techniques

Fourier-transformed infrared (FTIR) spectra were collected on a Nicolet iS5 spectrometer using a Smart Orbit ZnSe ATR accessory under nitrogen flow. Samples were deposited directly onto the crystal face, and spectra were collected at 4 cm⁻¹ resolution by summing 32 scans. Spline baseline corrections and Savitzky-Golay smoothing (with 25-point convolution) were applied.

Raman spectra were acquired using a DXR™3 Raman microscope (Thermo Scientific) with a 785nm laser. The studied sample in the form of dispersion was first drop-cast onto a gold substrate and dried. The sample spectrum was then acquired at 50x magnification at a laser power of 2 mW. Second-order polynomial fluorescence corrections were applied using the OMNIC software.

XPS measurements were conducted using a Nexsa G2 XPS system (Thermo Scientific) equipped with a monochromatic Al K_α X-ray source ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV). All spectra were acquired under ultra-high vacuum conditions (1.2×10^{-7} Pa) at room temperature (20 °C). The analyzed area on each sample was a circular spot with a diameter of 200 μm. Survey spectra were collected using a pass energy of 150.00 eV and a step size of 1.0 eV, while high-resolution spectra were acquired with a pass energy of 50.00 eV and a step size of 0.1 eV. To prevent surface charging and ensure accurate peak positioning, a dual-beam charge compensation system (low-energy electrons and low-energy ions) was employed throughout all measurements. Data acquisition and preliminary analysis were performed using the Thermo Scientific Avantage software (version 6.8.1). High-resolution spectra were further processed using MagicPlot software for peak deconvolution, following Shirley background subtraction performed in OriginPro.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded on the Aeris diffractometer (Malvern PANalytical, Ltd, USA) in the Bragg–Brentano geometry (iron-filtered Co K_α radiation: $\lambda = 0.178901$ nm, 40 kV and 15 mA). Samples were placed on a zero-background Si slide, gently pressed with sheet glass to create a uniform surface layer, and scanned with a step size of 0.0217° within a scan range from 5° to 105°. Thermal

analysis was performed using a STA449 C Jupiter Netzsch instrument at a heating rate of $10 \text{ K}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ under N_2 flow ($100 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) imaging was accomplished using a JEOL 2100 TEM instrument (JEOL, Japan) with an accelerating voltage of 200 kV.

2.5. Catalytic testing

A screw-top open-air tube was charged with 0.5 mmol of imidazole, 1 mmol of phenylboronic acid, and copper catalyst (5 mol.% of copper with respect to imidazole). Then, 3 mL of MeOH was put into the tube, followed by 1 mmol of Et_3N . The mixture was heated at 60°C for 20 h. For turnover frequency (TOF) determination, a 1-hour reaction was performed. After that, the mixture was centrifuged, and the pellet was washed twice with MeOH. The supernatants were combined, topped to 10 mL, and analyzed with GC (Agilent 6820) with nitrobenzene as internal standard. The catalyst was further washed with acetone, EtOH, water (3x), and MeOH and reused in another run.

The GC analysis of the mixtures from catalytic testing was done on an Agilent 6820 instrument with a DB-5HT column, N_2 carrier gas, and FID detection. The quantification of 1-phenylimidazole was done using a

calibration method using nitrobenzene as an internal standard. The purity of the 1-phenylimidazole standard used for the calibration was assessed using qNMR spectroscopy using a dimethyl sulfone certified standard (TraceCERT®, Sigma Aldrich). NMR measurements were done on a JNM-ECZ400R instrument (JEOL) with a superconducting coil having a magnetic field of 9.4 T (working frequency: 399.8 MHz for ^1H and 100.5 MHz for ^{13}C NMR) and a 5mm liquid probe.

TOF was calculated based on the total amount of copper present in the reaction mixture (n_{Cu}), the amount of product formed (n_{prod}), and the reaction time (t). The amounts of substrate (n_{subst}) and copper were constant across all experiments. Specifically, copper was used in a fixed amount of 5 mol% relative to the imidazole substrate. Under these conditions, the TOF could be directly calculated from the observed yield using the following relation:

$$\text{TOF} = \frac{n_{\text{prod}}}{n_{\text{Cu}} \cdot t} = \frac{\text{yield}(\%)/100 \cdot n_{\text{subst}}}{0.05 \cdot n_{\text{subst}} \cdot t} = \frac{\text{yield}(\%)}{5 \cdot t}$$

2.6. Computation methods

To explore possible reaction pathways of FG functionalization with PhenA, density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed

Fig. 1. Synthesis, TEM imaging of the G-Phen, and the reaction mechanism of the G-Phen synthesis: (a) schematic depiction of the reaction of fluorographene (FG) with 1,10-phenanthroline-5-amine resulting in 1,10-phenanthroline-functionalized graphene (G-Phen), (b-d) TEM images display flakes of the synthesized G-Phen material, and (e-f) reaction mechanisms of the radical and nucleophilic attack (e) on a radical center in FG and (f) at the boundary between the fluorinated and defluorinated region. Fluorine atoms are light blue, carbon grey, nitrogen dark blue, and hydrogen white. Numbers are reaction energies in $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.

using the Gaussian16 software [17]. The ground state geometries of all the investigated species were optimized using the ω B97X-D functional [18] in combination with the 6-31++G(d,p) basis set [19]. For open-shell systems, the spin-unrestricted formalism was employed. The impact of DMSO as the reaction medium was accounted for using the universal continuum solvation model based on solute electron density (SMD) [20]. As a model of the FG sheet, a circumpyrene molecule functionalized with varying numbers of fluorine atoms in *trans* positions on both sides of the structure was used (Fig. S1).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis and characterization of G-Phen

The G-Phen material was synthesized using well-established fluorographene (FG) chemistry, which enables the substitution of fluorine atoms by nucleophiles, typically accompanied by partial defluorination of the carbon backbone. In this case, 1,10-phenanthroline-5-amine (PhenA) was grafted onto the FG surface via its nucleophilic amine group (Fig. 1a). In contrast to earlier protocols that predominantly employed hazardous solvents such as DMF, we developed a greener

Fig. 2. Characterization of G-Phen: (a) FTIR spectra of PhenA and G-Phen with the far IR region in the inset, (b) Raman spectra of PhenA and G-Phen, (c) thermal analysis (thermogravimetric and differential thermogravimetric curves) of G-Phen under N₂ atmosphere, (d) survey XPS spectrum of G-Phen with the determined composition in the inset, deconvolution of C 1s (e) and N 1s (f) HR-XPS spectra of G-Phen with the areas of the individual components indicated in the insets.

method employing DMSO in combination with triethylamine as the base, enabling efficient defluorination under mild conditions [21]. To mitigate contamination by silicon-based species from glassware during the reaction, potassium carbonate was used to scavenge the liberated fluoride anions. The decomposition of K_2CO_3 further contributes to surface porosity enhancement by releasing CO_2 , thereby increasing the surface area of the resulting material [22].

The morphology of G-Phen mirrors that of the starting graphite fluoride precursor. The material consists of multilayered graphene-like sheets exhibiting a broad size distribution, ranging from hundreds of nanometers to several micrometers (Fig. 1b). TEM imaging reveals wrinkled edges and indistinct layer boundaries (Figs. 1b-d), which reflect the inherently defective structure of the material.

To elucidate the mechanism underlying the attachment of the PhenA functionality to the emerging graphene surface, density functional theory (DFT) simulations were conducted using models that included FG with radical point defects and partially defluorinated regions (Fig. S1). The latter were considered due to the known role of triethylamine (Et_3N) in promoting defluorination under reaction conditions [21].

The simulations revealed that successful covalent binding of PhenA to FG requires prior activation of the PhenA molecule via two distinct pathways. In the first pathway, interaction between FG radical point defects and PhenA (Fig. S2a) generates a thermodynamically favorable route for the resulting PhenA radical to react with either additional radical sites or defluorinated regions on the FG surface. Both reaction channels lead to stable covalent attachment of PhenA to the emerging graphene framework (Fig. 1e, f). In general, the extent of defluorination positively correlates with the favorability of the attachment process (Fig. S3).

In the second activation pathway, K_2CO_3 deprotonates PhenA, forming a PhenA anion (Fig. S2b, c). This anionic form can also engage with defluorinated FG regions via a similar reaction mechanism, though with lower thermodynamic favorability compared to the radical pathway (Fig. 1e, f, and Fig. S3). Notably, a comparable anionic attachment mechanism has previously been reported in the context of polysulfide functionalization of partially defluorinated FG [23].

The FTIR spectrum of G-Phen shows a band at 1565 cm^{-1} , attributed to C=C stretching in sp^2 -hybridized carbon domains (Fig. 2a). A broad signal centered around 1200 cm^{-1} corresponds to various skeletal C-C vibrations, especially those associated with defect-rich regions [16]. The successful incorporation of phenanthroline units is evidenced by the characteristic out-of-plane (oop) C-H bending mode [24], whose position in the G-Phen spectrum aligns with that of free PhenA. In contrast to FTIR, Raman spectroscopy revealed no distinct bands assignable to PhenA moieties in G-Phen (Fig. 2b). The I_D/I_G ratio of 1.47 suggests a high degree of functionalization and/or a significantly defective carbon structure [25]. The defectivity of the G-Phen material likely stems from the parent graphite fluoride material, since it contains many structural defects apart from the fluorine vacancies [26,27]. This is supported by the solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance analysis, which proved the highly defective nature of the starting material (Fig. S5, ESI).

The degree of functionalization was estimated via thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) done under an inert atmosphere of N_2 . Following an initial mass loss of 0.7 % due to water desorption, the TGA curve showed two distinct weight losses occurring between $160\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with a total cumulative mass loss of 21.8 % in this range (Fig. 2c). The mass of the final residue at $1200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was 68.7 % of the original G-Phen material. Considering this and the XPS composition of the material synthesized under no presence of PhenA (Fig. S4), the functionalization degree has been estimated to range between 1.5 and 2.7 % (see ESI for details).

The elemental composition determined by XPS also revealed insights into the chemical environment within G-Phen (Fig. 2d). Carbon (83.1 at %) and nitrogen (9.2 at%) originate from the graphene framework and the phenanthroline-amine groups. Oxygen contamination (5.7 at%) is attributed to the hygroscopic nature of DMSO and the use of non-inert

conditions, leading to the formation of hydroxyl functionalities. The remaining 1.8 at% fluorine reflects the high degree of defluorination achieved under the applied reaction conditions. Minor chlorine content is attributed to residual HCl from the acid-washing step, likely resulting from ammonium chloride formation due to protonation of the secondary amine groups linking phenanthroline to the carbon matrix.

The high-resolution C 1s XPS spectrum of G-Phen (Fig. 2e) shows a dominant peak at 284.1 eV, attributed to sp^2/sp^3 hybridized C-C bonds (57.4 %). Due to the disordered nature of the carbon domains, distinguishing between sp^2 and sp^3 carbon is inherently challenging [28]. A peak at 285.2 eV corresponds to additional sp^3 carbon and to sp^2 carbon of the phenanthroline rings, which was substantiated by separate measurement of PhenA exhibiting C 1s maximum at the same position (Fig. S6). The 286.4 eV component is associated primarily with C-N bonds connecting the Phen functionalities to the graphene backbone [22]. Contributions from C=O and residual C-F functionalities are visible at 287–290 eV [29]. The high-energy tail above 290 eV is attributed to the $\pi-\pi^*$ shakeup satellite, indicating the presence of extended sp^2 carbon networks [30].

The high-resolution N 1s spectrum (Fig. 2f) shows a dominant component at 398.2 eV (56.4 %), typical of pyridinic nitrogen within phenanthroline rings [31]. A second peak at 399.5 eV (39.6 %) corresponds to secondary amines [32], which may also include minor contributions from triethylamine residues or other nitrogen species. This also applies to a minor signal at 401.4 eV, which is assigned to graphitic nitrogen [31]. The observed nitrogen distribution is consistent with the expected stoichiometry of the phenanthroline ligand, with a pyridinic to secondary amine ratio close to 2:1.

3.2. Metal anchoring and catalyst characterization

Copper anchoring was achieved following the same procedure previously reported for cyanographene (G-CN), involving impregnation of the material with an aqueous solution of copper(II) chloride ($CuCl_2$) (Fig. 3a). After removal of non-adsorbed copper via thorough washing, changes in the far IR spectral region of the resulting catalyst, denoted as G-Phen-Cu, indicated successful coordination. Specifically, the out-of-plane (oop) C-H bending band underwent a splitting: the intensity of the original peak at 739 cm^{-1} decreased, while a new band appeared at 729 cm^{-1} (Fig. 3b). This newly emerged lower-energy band is attributed to Phen functionalities coordinating to copper centers, indicating that copper is indeed anchored at the designed binding sites.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis revealed an increase in both chlorine and oxygen content upon copper incorporation (Fig. 3c), suggesting the formation of a coordination complex involving Phen ligands, chloride, and aqua ligands. The low chlorine content observed implies a predominant Cu(I) oxidation state, as fewer chloride counterions would be required for charge compensation. This hypothesis is supported by high-resolution Cu 2p XPS spectra, which show an almost complete absence of Cu(II)-related satellite features (Fig. 3d), indicating that copper is mainly present in a reduced state [33]. However, the Cu $2p_{3/2}$ binding energy at 931.8 eV alone does not unambiguously identify the oxidation state of copper. Therefore, further analysis was conducted using the Cu LMM Auger transition. The maximum of the Auger line was detected at a binding energy of 570.68 eV (inset of Fig. 3d). With Al $K\alpha$ radiation ($h\nu = 1486.6\text{ eV}$) used for the measurement, this corresponds to a kinetic energy of 915.92 eV. The modified Auger parameter (α'), defined as $\alpha' = E_k(Cu\text{ LMM}) + E_B(Cu\ 2p_{3/2})$, is calculated to be 1847.72 eV. This value is in excellent agreement with that reported for copper(I) chloride ($\alpha' = 1847.51\text{ eV}$), thus confirming that the dominant oxidation state of copper in G-Phen-Cu is +1 [33].

The reduction of copper upon anchoring has been previously reported in similar systems based on G-CN [13,15], where electron transfer from the graphene substrate to the metal atom was identified as

Fig. 3. Synthesis and characterization of G-Ph-Cu: (a) Schematic depiction of copper anchoring onto G-Phen with a model structure of the created complex, (b) the changes in the far IR region of Phen oop C-H bending caused by the Cu anchoring, (c) survey XPS spectrum of G-Phen-Cu with elemental composition in the inset, (d) deconvolution of HR-XPS of Cu 2p region of G-Phen-Cu with Cu LMM Auger line in the inset, and (e) comparison of XRD patterns of G-Phen and G-Phen-Cu with TEM image of G-Phen-Cu in the inset.

the driving force. The in-situ reduction of Cu(II) during the XPS measurement was excluded through electron paramagnetic resonance experiments, proving the mixed valence system of copper within the G-CN-Cu [13]. Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) further supported the single-atom nature of the anchored copper species. The XRD pattern of G-Phen-Cu was indistinguishable from that of the pristine G-Phen support, with no diffraction peaks corresponding to crystalline copper-based phases (Fig. 3e). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) imaging also showed no evidence of high-contrast metal clusters or particles (inset of Fig. 3e), reinforcing the conclusion that copper is atomically dispersed within the G-Phen matrix.

3.2.1. Catalytic performance of G-Phen-Cu in Chan-Lam coupling

The catalytic activity of G-Phen-Cu was evaluated in the functionalization of imidazole via Chan-Lam (CL) coupling (Fig. 4a). This reaction serves as an alternative to Buchwald-Hartwig amination of organic halides, which typically requires palladium-based catalysts [34]. Given that CL coupling can be catalyzed by various copper species, both homogeneous and heterogeneous, it was chosen as the model reaction to validate our proof-of-concept strategy for single-metal-atom heterogenization.

The copper loading was maintained at 5 mol.% relative to imidazole (0.5 mmol per reaction). Methanol was selected as the reaction solvent due to its known compatibility with CL coupling, despite its potential to act as a competing substrate. To mitigate this effect, an excess (1 mmol)

Fig. 4. Catalytic testing and characterization of the recovered G-Ph-Cu: (a) scheme of the CL reaction used for the G-Phen-Cu catalyst testing, (b) comparison of the catalytic activities of G-Phen-Cu and G-CN-Cu in CL coupling, and their recycling determined using GC, (c) powder X-ray diffractogram of the recovered G-Phen-Cu and its TEM image in the inset, (d) survey XPS spectrum of the recovered G-Phen-Cu with its elemental composition in the inset, and (e) comparison of the FIR regions of the FTIR spectra of the fresh and recovered G-Phen-Cu catalyst.

of the phenylboronic acid was used. Triethylamine was employed to provide the basic conditions favorable for the reaction.

In the initial experiment, the G-Phen-Cu catalyst afforded a quantitative yield of 1-phenylimidazole. In contrast, the G-CN-Cu catalyst, prepared analogously to G-Phen-Cu from G-CN, exhibited significantly lower activity under identical conditions (Fig. 4b). Upon recycling, G-Phen-Cu maintained its activity in the second cycle, with minor reductions observed in the third and fourth runs. Beyond the fourth cycle, catalytic performance declined significantly, and testing was discontinued after six runs.

Post-reaction analysis of the recovered catalyst revealed that the activity loss could not be attributed to copper aggregation, as evidenced by unchanged powder X-ray diffraction patterns and TEM imaging (Fig. 4c). Instead, the decline was attributed to copper leaching, as supported by ICP-MS analysis. The Cu content decreased from 4.32 wt% in the fresh catalyst to 2.78 wt% after six cycles.

In addition, the G-Ph support itself was found to undergo partial chemical modification under the applied reaction conditions. XPS of the used catalyst showed further defluorination of the graphene scaffold (Fig. 4d), accompanied by a reduction in nitrogen content by 1.2 at%. This corresponds to a 14 % decrease relative to the initial nitrogen content and suggests partial degradation or loss of the Phen ligands or

other N-containing groups. These findings imply that copper loss may result from the detachment of intact Cu-Phen complexes rather than the leaching of isolated copper atoms. A possible driving force for this process is the substitution of the Phen ligands by phenyl-containing intermediates derived from phenylboronic acid. Supporting this hypothesis, a new infrared absorption band appeared at 696 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the recovered material (Fig. 4e), which is tentatively assigned to phenyl group incorporation. This modification likely occurs through a reaction between boronic acid-derived intermediates and the secondary amine linkers that connect the Phen units to the graphene backbone, leading to anchoring of phenyl groups at sites originally occupied by the Phen ligands.

In contrast, the G-CN-Cu catalyst, although showing lower catalytic activity in the cross-coupling reaction, exhibited significantly less copper loss. The copper content decreased only slightly from 3.53 wt% in the fresh material to 3.26 wt% in the recovered sample. Given the less stable monodentate binding mode of copper in G-CN-Cu, the more pronounced copper leaching observed in G-Ph-Cu supports the hypothesis that the drop in copper content is caused by the detachment of entire Cu-Phen complexes rather than by simple ionic leaching.

To benchmark the catalytic activity of G-Phen-Cu, turnover frequency (TOF) was determined by performing a 1-hour reaction. The

resulting yield was 19 %, corresponding to a TOF of 3.8 h⁻¹. A comparison of the G-Phen-Cu activity with that of common Cu species is summarized in Table 1. While G-Phen-Cu substantially outperformed other tested heterogeneous systems such as G-CN-Cu (TOF = 0.03 h⁻¹) and commercial CuO nanoparticles (<50 nm, TOF = 0.13 h⁻¹), its activity remained nearly one order of magnitude lower than that of CuCl₂, which achieved a 99.3 % yield (TOF = 19.9 h⁻¹) under the same conditions. The addition of free Phen ligand to the reaction mixture did not enhance catalytic performance. Given the predominant Cu(I) state in G-Phen-Cu, CuCl and CuI were tested to assess the intrinsic activity of Cu(I) species, yielding TOFs of 12.7 and 10.0 h⁻¹, respectively. Although both were less active than CuCl₂, their higher activity compared to G-Phen-Cu suggests that the Cu(I) oxidation state is not inherently responsible for its lower performance. Instead, the reduced activity of G-Phen-Cu is likely due to limited accessibility of its active Cu-Phen sites compared to those in homogeneous systems.

In terms of TOF, G-Phen-Cu demonstrates moderate catalytic activity compared to other reported heterogeneous systems for CL N-arylation of imidazole (Table 2). Its performance is comparable to that of CuCl₂ immobilized on polyacrylonitrile fibers [35]. The most active heterogeneous catalyst reported to date for this transformation is a Cu(II) Schiff base complex immobilized on cellulose [36].

4. Conclusion

We report the successful covalent functionalization of fluorographene with 1,10-phenanthroline-5-amine, yielding well-defined anchoring sites for atomically dispersed metal species. Copper ions were effectively coordinated by the graphene surface conjugated bidentate phenanthroline ligands, affording a single-atom catalyst G-Phen-Cu. Comprehensive characterization confirmed that copper was present as isolated Cu(I) species, stabilized by coordination with phenanthroline moieties, with no detectable (nano)crystalline copper phases, as evidenced by XRD and TEM analyses.

Catalytic performance of G-Phen-Cu was evaluated in the Chan–Lam coupling for the N-arylation of imidazole, achieving TOF of 3.8 h⁻¹. This performance surpasses that of analogous systems such as G-CN-Cu and commercial CuO nanoparticles, although it remains below that of homogeneous CuCl₂ or CuCl. Recyclability assessments revealed a gradual decline in catalytic activity, attributed primarily to copper leaching rather than sintering, as confirmed by ICP-MS, XRD, and TEM. Additional analyses suggest that the leaching may involve the release of intact Cu–Phen complexes rather than isolated copper ions.

These findings demonstrate that the covalent conjugation of polydentate ligands provides a promising strategy for the development of SACs with well-defined active sites. However, to fully harness the potential of such systems, improvements in catalyst stability and reusability are essential. Enhancements may be achieved through the introduction of secondary anchoring groups (e.g., adjacent nitrogen or oxygen donors) to form chelating or macrocyclic environments, exploration of alternative metalation methods beyond aqueous impregnation, and post-synthetic modifications such as mild annealing or covalent crosslinking to reinforce metal–ligand interactions and minimize leaching. These strategies offer a pathway toward robust, rationally designed SACs on carbon-based supports with high catalytic performance and long-term operational stability.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Radek Zboril: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization. **Michal Otyepka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization. **Vítězslav Hrubý:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Dagmar Zaoralová:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Table 1

Catalytic activity in terms of turnover frequency (TOF) of various catalytic systems tested using CL functionalization of imidazole.

Type	Catalyst	Time (h)	Yield (%)	TOF* (h ⁻¹)
Heterogeneous	G-Phen-Cu	1	19.0	3.8
	G-CN-Cu	20	3.3	0.03
	CuO NPs (50nm)	20	13.2	0.13
Homogeneous	CuCl ₂	1	99.3	19.9
	[Cu(phen)]Cl ₂	1	93.3	18.7
	CuCl	1	63.3	12.7
	CuI	1	49.8	10.0

Table 2

TOFs of the heterogeneous catalysts reported in the literature.

Ref#	Heterogeneous catalyst	TOF (h ⁻¹)
[37]	Cu ₃ (BTC) ₂ MOF	0.56
[38]	[Cu ₃₀ I ₁₆ (mtpmt) ₁₂ (μ ₁₀ -S ₄)] clusters	39.6
[39]	CuO NPs	0.59
[40]	Cu@KF-C/CoFe ₂ O ₄	12.12
[35]	CuCl ₂ @PAN _{PA-2} F	4.08
[41]	Cu/PVPI25	2.35
[42]	CuO/t-ZrO ₂	2.00
[36]	Cell-AP-Cu(II)	872.70
This work	G-Phen-Cu	3.80

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: MO has share in ATOMIVER (Czechia) and InSiliBio (France) companies. Other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115493](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115493)

Data availability

The publication data will be made available at ZENODO after manuscript acceptance.

References

- [1] X.-F. Yang, A. Wang, B. Qiao, J. Li, J. Liu, T. Zhang, Single-Atom catalysts: a new frontier in heterogeneous catalysis, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 46 (2013) 1740–1748, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ar300361m>.
- [2] M. Kottwitz, Y. Li, H. Wang, A.I. Frenkel, R.G. Nuzzo, Single atom catalysts: a review of characterization methods, *Chem. Methods* 1 (2021) 278–294, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cmt.202100020>.
- [3] D. Roy, K. Deori, Structure–activity relationships in the development of single atom catalysts for sustainable organic transformations, *Nanoscale Adv.* 7 (2025) 1243–1271, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4NA00433G>.

- [4] Z. Ma, C. Kuloor, C. Kreyenschulte, S. Bartling, O. Malina, M. Haumann, P. W. Menezes, R. Zboril, M. Beller, R.V. Jagadeesh, Development of Iron-Based single atom materials for general and efficient synthesis of amines, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 63 (2024) e202407859, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202407859>.
- [5] Y. Pan, Y. Chen, K. Wu, Z. Chen, S. Liu, X. Cao, W.-C. Cheong, T. Meng, J. Luo, L. Zheng, C. Liu, D. Wang, Q. Peng, J. Li, C. Chen, Regulating the coordination structure of single-atom Fe-NxCy catalytic sites for benzene oxidation, *Nat. Commun.* 10 (2019) 4290, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-12362-8>.
- [6] D. Zaoralová, R. Langer, M. Otyepka, Iron Single-Atom catalysts anchored on Defect-Engineered N-Doped graphene reveal an interplay between CO₂ reduction activity and stability, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscuschemeng.5c01417>.
- [7] J. Li, Q. Guan, H. Wu, W. Liu, Y. Lin, Z. Sun, X. Ye, X. Zheng, H. Pan, J. Zhu, S. Chen, W. Zhang, S. Wei, J. Lu, Highly active and stable metal Single-Atom catalysts achieved by strong electronic Metal-Support interactions, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 141 (2019) 14515–14519, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.9b06482>.
- [8] M. Melchionna, P. Fornasiero, On the tracks to “Smart” Single-Atom catalysts, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 147 (2025) 2275–2290, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.4c15803>.
- [9] J.-F. Sun, J.-T. Wu, Q.-Q. Xu, D. Zhou, J.-Z. Yin, CO₂ electrochemical reduction using single-atom catalysts. Preparation, characterization and anchoring strategies: a review, *Environ. Chem. Lett.* 18 (2020) 1593–1623, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-020-01023-8>.
- [10] S. Mehmood, S. Sk, B.M. Abraham, M. Ahmadipour, U. Pal, J. Dutta, Recent advances in Single-Atom catalyst for solar energy conversion: a comprehensive review and future outlook, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 35 (2025) 2418602, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202418602>.
- [11] M.B. Gawande, P. Fornasiero, R. Zboril, Carbon-Based Single-Atom catalysts for advanced applications, *ACS Catal.* 10 (2020) 2231–2259, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.9b04217>.
- [12] D. Matochová, M. Medved', A. Bakandritsos, T. Steklý, R. Zboril, M. Otyepka, 2D chemistry: chemical control of graphene derivatization, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 9 (2018) 3580–3585, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.8b01596>.
- [13] A. Bakandritsos, R.G. Kadam, P. Kumar, G. Zoppellaro, M. Medved', J. Tuček, T. Montini, O. Tomanec, P. Andryšková, B. Drahoš, R.S. Varma, M. Otyepka, M. B. Gawande, P. Fornasiero, R. Zboril, Mixed-Valence Single-Atom catalyst derived from functionalized graphene, *Adv. Mater.* 31 (2019) 1900323, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201900323>.
- [14] R.G. Kadam, T. Zhang, D. Zaoralová, M. Medved', A. Bakandritsos, O. Tomanec, M. Petr, J. Zhu Chen, J.T. Miller, M. Otyepka, R. Zboril, T. Asefa, M.B. Gawande, Single Co-Atoms as electrocatalysts for efficient hydrazine oxidation reaction, *Small* 17 (2021) 2006477, <https://doi.org/10.1002/smll.202006477>.
- [15] R.G. Kadam, M. Medved', S. Kumar, D. Zaoralová, G. Zoppellaro, Z. Bad'ura, T. Montini, A. Bakandritsos, E. Fonda, O. Tomanec, M. Otyepka, R.S. Varma, M. B. Gawande, P. Fornasiero, R. Zboril, Linear-Structure Single-Atom Gold(I) catalyst for dehydrogenative coupling of organosilanes with alcohols, *ACS Catal.* 13 (2023) 16067–16077, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.3c03937>.
- [16] A. Bakandritsos, M. Pykal, P. Błoński, P. Jakubec, D.D. Chronopoulos, K. Poláková, V. Georgakilas, K. Čépe, O. Tomanec, V. Ranc, A.B. Bourlinos, R. Zboril, M. Otyepka, Cyanographene and graphene acid: emerging derivatives enabling High-Yield and selective functionalization of graphene, *ACS Nano* 11 (2017) 2982–2991, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.6b08449>.
- [17] M.J. Frisch, G.W. Trucks, H.B. Schlegel, G.E. Scuseria, M.A. Robb, J.R. Cheeseman, G. Scalmani, V. Barone, G.A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, et al., *Gaussian 16 Revis. C.01* (2016).
- [18] J.-D. Chai, M. Head-Gordon, Long-range corrected hybrid density functionals with damped atom-atom dispersion corrections, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 10 (2008) 6615–6620, <https://doi.org/10.1039/B810189B>.
- [19] R. Ditchfield, W.J. Hehre, J.A. Pople, Self-consistent molecular-orbital methods. IX. an extended Gaussian-type basis for molecular-orbital studies of organic molecules, *J. Chem. Phys.* 54 (1971) 724–728, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1674902>.
- [20] A.V. Marenich, C.J. Cramer, D.G. Truhlar, Universal solvation model based on solute electron density and on a continuum model of the solvent defined by the bulk dielectric constant and atomic surface tensions, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 113 (2009) 6378–6396, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp810292n>.
- [21] V.P. Mel'nikov, D.P. Shashkin, A.N. Shchegolikhin, Defluorination of fluorinated coke by triethylamine, *Dokl. Chem.* 421 (2008) 182–185, <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0012500808080041>.
- [22] E.C. Vermisoglou, P. Jakubec, A. Bakandritsos, V. Kupka, M. Pykal, V. Šedajová, J. Vlček, O. Tomanec, M. Scheibe, R. Zboril, M. Otyepka, Graphene with covalently grafted amino acid as a route toward Eco-Friendly and sustainable supercapacitors, *ChemSusChem* 14 (2021) 3904–3914, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.202101039>.
- [23] I. Tantis, A. Bakandritsos, D. Zaoralová, M. Medved', P. Jakubec, J. Havláková, R. Zboril, M. Otyepka, Covalently interlinked graphene sheets with Sulfur-Chains enable superior Lithium-Sulfur battery cathodes at Full-Mass level, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 31 (2021) 2101326, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202101326>.
- [24] M. Margoshes, V.A. Fassel, The infrared spectra of aromatic compounds: I. The out-of-plane C-H bending vibrations in the region 625–900 cm⁻¹, *Spectrochim. Acta* 7 (1955) 14–24, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0371-1951\(55\)80003-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0371-1951(55)80003-3).
- [25] S.P. Economopoulos, G. Rotas, Y. Miyata, H. Shinohara, N. Tagmatarchis, Exfoliation and chemical modification using microwave irradiation affording highly functionalized graphene, *ACS Nano* 4 (2010) 7499–7507, <https://doi.org/10.1021/nn101735e>.
- [26] P. Lazar, V. Hrubý, M. Petr, Z. Bad'ura, G. Zoppellaro, M. Otyepka, Decoding structural characteristics of fluorinated graphene via Computer-Aided spectroscopic analysis, *Carbon* 243 (2025) 120567, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2025.120567>.
- [27] B.J. Walder, T.M. Alam, Modes of disorder in Poly(carbon monofluoride), *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 143 (2021) 11714–11733, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.1c05234>.
- [28] B. Lesiak, L. Kövér, J. Tóth, J. Zemek, P. Jiricek, A. Kromka, N. Rangam, C sp²/sp³ hybridisations in carbon nanomaterials – XPS and (X)AES study, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 452 (2018) 223–231, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2018.04.269>.
- [29] E.C. Vermisoglou, P. Jakubec, A. Bakandritsos, M. Pykal, S. Talande, V. Kupka, R. Zboril, M. Otyepka, Chemical tuning of specific capacitance in functionalized fluorographene, *Chem. Mater.* 31 (2019) 4698–4709, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.9b00655>.
- [30] D.D. Chronopoulos, C. Stangel, M. Scheibe, K. Cepe, N. Tagmatarchis, M. Otyepka, Electrocatalytic activity for proton reduction by a covalent non-metal graphene-fullerene hybrid, *Chem. Commun.* 58 (2022) 8396–8399, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2cc02272a>.
- [31] P. Lazar, R. Mach, M. Otyepka, Spectroscopic fingerprints of graphitic, pyrrolic, pyridinic, and chemisorbed nitrogen in N-Doped graphene, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 123 (2019) 10695–10702, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.9b02163>.
- [32] N. Graf, E. Yegen, T. Gross, A. Lippitz, W. Weigel, S. Krakert, A. Terfort, W.E. S. Unger, XPS and NEXAFS studies of aliphatic and aromatic amine species on functionalized surfaces, *Surf. Sci.* 603 (2009) 2849–2860, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susc.2009.07.029>.
- [33] M.C. Biesinger, Advanced analysis of copper X-ray photoelectron spectra, *Surf. Interface Anal.* 49 (2017) 1325–1334, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sia.6239>.
- [34] P.S. Devi, S. Saranya, G. Anilkumar, Recent advances in Chan-Lam coupling reaction, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 14 (2024) 2320–2351, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4CY00034J>.
- [35] C. Zhang, H. Zhu, K. Gang, M. Tao, N. Ma, W. Zhang, Immobilization of copper(II) into polyacrylonitrile fiber toward efficient and recyclable catalyst in Chan-Lam coupling reactions, *React. Funct. Polym.* 160 (2021) 104831, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reactfunctpolym.2021.104831>.
- [36] P.S. Phrande, P.M. Mhalidar, T.R. Lohar, S.K. Ghotekar, T.N. Chhowala, G. S. Rashinkar, D.M. Pore, A selective heterogeneous cellulose supported schiff base Cu(II) catalyst for Chan-Evans-Lam coupling, *Res. Chem. Inter.* 49 (2023) 4541–4560, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11164-023-05089-1>.
- [37] N. Anbu, A. Dhakshinamoorthy, Cu₃(BTC)₂ metal-organic framework catalyzed N-arylation of benzimidazoles and imidazoles with phenylboronic acid, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* 65 (2018) 120–126, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiec.2018.04.020>.
- [38] H.-X. Li, W. Zhao, H.-Y. Li, Z.-L. Xu, W.-X. Wang, J.-P. Lang, [Cu₃O₁₁(mtpmt)₁₂(μ₁₀-S₄)]: an unusual 30-membered copper(I) cluster derived from the C–S bond cleavage and its use in heterogeneous catalysis, *Chem. Commun.* 49 (2013) 4259–4261, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C2CC36736J>.
- [39] R. Borah, P. Raul, A. Mahanta, A. Shchukarev, J.-P. Mikkola, A. Thakur, Copper oxide nanoparticles as a mild and efficient catalyst for N-Arylation of imidazole and aniline with boronic acids at room temperature, *Synlett* 28 (2017) 1177–1182, <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0036-1588741>.
- [40] S. Sharma, M. Kaur, C. Sharma, A. Choudhary, S. Paul, Biomass-derived activated carbon-supported copper catalyst: an efficient heterogeneous magnetic catalyst for base-free Chan-Lam coupling and oxidations, *ACS Omega* 6 (2021) 19529–19545, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.1c01830>.
- [41] A.Yu. Mitrofanov, A.V. Murashkina, A.I. Barabanova, A.V. Vorozheykina, Y. V. Zubavichus, A.R. Khokhlov, I.P. Beletskaya, Efficient recyclable Cu-catalysts for click reaction and Chan-Lam coupling based on copolymers of N-vinylimidazole with N-vinylcaprolactam, *Mol. Catal.* 541 (2023) 112915, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcat.2023.112915>.
- [42] M. Kondo, T. Joutsuka, K. Fujiwara, T. Honma, M. Nishijima, S. Tada, Catalysis of surface dispersed Cu²⁺ species on t-ZrO₂: square-planar Cu catalyzed cross-coupling of arylboronic acid and imidazole, *Catal. Sci. Technol.* 13 (2023) 2247–2254, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3CY00024A>.